

**IVANA KUPALA IN MALLET:
AN UKRAINIAN (RE)INVENTED TRADITION IN
BRAZIL**

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ABSTRACT. The aim objective of the article is to study the problematics related to the *Ivana Kupala* ritual-festival in Mallet, Paraná, Brazil, examining aspects of culture, memory, and concepts related to tradition, invented/(re)invented tradition proposed by Hobsbawn and Ranger (1984). Organized by the Folkloric Group *Spomen* and the Ukrainian immigrant community since 2002, this unique celebration combines theatricality, rich semiotic symbols, and a juxtaposition of pagan rituals within a Catholic backdrop. Drawing inspiration from Bhabha's (2007) and Harvey's (2003) insights on the cultural impact on identity, the research explores the hybrid nature of culture, emphasizing the dynamic preservation of the Ukrainian cultural traits, including language and folk dances, among descendants in a post-colonial context. The concept of folklore experiencing first and second existences, as proposed by Nahachevky (2001) and Puh (2017), further enhances our understanding of the evolving traditions and their influence on community cultural practices.

KEYWORDS: *Ivana Kupala*, cultural hybridism, identity, folklore, tradition, Ukrainian community, post-colonialism.

In the city of Mallet, in the Central-Southern region of the state of Paraná – Brazil, the Folkloric Group *Spomen*, along with the community of descendants of Ukrainian immigrants and the general community, has been celebrating a slightly unconventional June period festival since 2002. The already traditional *Ivana Kupala* festival increasingly attracts people to the event and has started to gain prominence in the news due to its eccentricity. Some highlights that captures attention at the event are the wealth of richly identified symbols and the theatricality. This richness is so

extensive that, for this presentation, we need to narrow our focus only to aspects related to tradition; otherwise, the work would expand into other realms, such as semiotics and theater. Furthermore, we reflect on another detail: the occurrence of a pagan festival in the courtyard of the Catholic church. The rituals trace back to times preceding Christianity; mythological, folkloric, and mystical characters blend with the spectators, all enlivened by cheerful Ukrainian music and dance, as well as *Gaucha* – a traditional dance from the state of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil.

The presence of pagan elements in a Christian environment took time to be accepted by the community in the city of Mallet. Consequently, studies focused on culture and tradition aim to strengthen the identity of Ukrainian descendants in the region. In David Harvey's perspective, the interference of culture in the identity of a people is evident. According to Harvey, understanding one's own culture legitimizes diverse social groups, especially the more excluded ones, as they speak for themselves, amplifying the comprehension of difference and alterity. This conception also deepens the liberating potential it offers to an array of new social movements (Harvey, 2003, p. 52)¹⁹.

Further delving into identity and culture concepts, it is crucial to consider issues related to cultural hybridism. As stated by Bhabha (2007), identities emerge from a sense of incompleteness that is gradually filled by external influences, often shaped by how we imagine being perceived by others. This phenomenon occurs because we are consistently (re)constructing our identity. This factor is evidenced in *Ivana Kupala* by the presence of the *Gaucha* tradition, for example, as well as by elements identified in other Brazilian folk plays.

The concept of identity we will use in this text is considered through hybridity. Following Bhabha's theories, culture is not a static entity, unable to be crystallized in time and space, leading us to look beyond the origins of culture and observe what happens when different cultures interact, such as the interaction between descendants of Ukrainian immigrants with Brazilian and Gaucho culture, and even their own culture erased from memory. According to Bhabha: «These 'in-between spaces' [...] initiate

¹⁹ “compreensão da diferença e da alteridade, bem como o potencial libertatório que ele oferece a todo um conjunto de novos movimentos sociais” (Harvey, 2003, p. 52).

new signs of identity and innovative positions of collaboration and contestation, in the act of defining the very idea of society» (Bhabha, 2007, p. 20)²⁰. It is in these interstices that we can identify the aspects that form the identity of a nation or community.

The evolution of traditions can be analyzed in various aspects, directly influencing the cultural practices of the community. However, in the *Ivana Kupala* festival in the city of Mallet, we perceive a deviation from the "original" Ukrainian model. We analyze the event, then, based on two concepts: the idea of the first and second existences of folklore by Nahachevsky (2001) and the concept of invented – or (re)invented – tradition by Hobsbawm and Ranger (1984).

Considering Nahachevsky's premises regarding folklore in first and second existences, Milan Puh analyzes the community of Ukrainian descendants in Brazil. According to Puh, Nahachevsky «defines folk dance in the first existence as an integral part of the community's life, while in the second existence, it is not fully connected to it. It is not the property of the entire community but of some interested individuals. Indeed, we can agree that Ukrainian folklore is no longer an integral part of the community, but there are elements of it that continue to have a constant and foundational presence in the community (in religious processions, celebrations of national dates, central events like Ukrainian Nights and Dances, etc.)» (Puh, 2017, p. 253–254)²¹.

Puh's analysis is crucial for the distinction presented in this study between *Ivana Kupala* still found in Ukraine, and the *Ivana Kupala* ritual-festival in Mallet. As a practice preserved by those who are interested in it – the Folkloric Group *Spomen – Ivana Kupala* in Mallet has lost some of its integration common to the entire community, classifying it as the «second existence» of folklore. The «preserved» folk manifestations, such as cuisine, language, art and rituals, continue in the lives of those descendants, although with varying intensity.

²⁰ “Esses ‘entre-lugares’ [...] dão início a novos signos de identidade e postos inovadores de colaboração e contestação, no ato de definir a própria ideia de sociedade” (Bhabha, 2007, p. 20).

²¹ Nahachevsky “define a dança folclórica na primeira existência como parte integral da vida da comunidade, enquanto na segunda não está ligada a ela integralmente. Não é propriedade da comunidade inteira, mas de alguns indivíduos interessados. E, de fato, podemos concordar que o folclore ucraniano não faz mais parte integralmente da comunidade, porém existem elementos seus que continuam com uma presença constante e fundante na comunidade (nas procissões religiosas, comemorações de datas nacionais, eventos centrais como as Noites e Bailes ucranianos etc.)” (Puh, 2017, p. 253-254).

Finally, we analyze the *Ivana Kupala* ritual-festival in Mallet from the perspective of a (re)invention, as its second existence of folklore distances it from the originally Ukrainian event. According to Hobsbawm and Ranger, "invented tradition" refers to a set of practices, typically governed by tacit or openly accepted rules. These ritualistic and symbolic practices aim to instill certain values and norms of behavior through repetition, which automatically implies continuity with the past (Hobsbawm; Ranger, 1984, p. 9)²². The traditional *Ivana Kupala* ritual-festival was readapted to a new reality and has become established, now considered a traditional event.

The event's creator, folklorist Andreiv Choma, initiated the *Ivana Kupala* ritual-festival in Mallet in 2002, adding characters and semiotic elements with each edition. Choma initiated, or rather, (re)invented a tradition, as the event in the new location became entirely different from the original. The «invented tradition» should be analyzed in conjunction with the concepts of multiculturalism and the potential tensions that this process entails. It is evident that the Ukrainian immigrants who arrived in Mallet brought beliefs and discourses rooted in their baggage, undoubtedly affected by conflicts between the original Slavic religion – with its polytheisms – and the Catholic Church, which also underwent significant changes during the process. A century after the arrival of the first Ukrainian immigrants in Brazil, remnants of these conflicts were still very apparent, especially when considering, according to Hall (2003), events such as the post-colonial question, post-Cold War effects, and globalization.

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²² “tradição inventada” entende-se um conjunto de práticas, normalmente reguladas por regras tácitas ou abertamente aceitas; tais práticas, de natureza ritual e simbólica, visam inculcar certos valores e normas de comportamento através da repetição, o que implica, automaticamente, uma continuidade em relação ao passado” (Hobsbawm; Ranger, 1984, p. 9).

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